

THROUGH PENELOPE'S EYES: FROM ATWOOD TO HOMER

The storyline and characters of Homer's *Odyssey* have had a long literary life, and most notable is the development of Penelope through the ages. In this paper, I will first look at Penelope as she appears in the Homeric poem, and next evaluate her character in Ovid's *Heroides*, Christine de Pizan's *The Book of the City of Ladies*, and Margaret Atwood's novella, *The Penelopiad*, three works highly reflective of their particular historical and cultural contexts. For each representation, I will point out the similarities and differences between Homer's Penelope and the later adaptations and try to elucidate the alterations—or lack thereof—to the original character.

In myth (according to Robert Graves), Penelope was born "Arnaea" or "Arnacia," to Icarus and the Naiad Periboea. Her father cast her into the sea as an infant; she was saved by "a flock of purple-striped ducks," at which point her parents decided to raise her. Years later, after Odysseus competed for, and won, her hand in marriage, her father chased the marriage chariot, but after Penelope drew her veil across her cheek to signal acceptance of her husband and new life, her father recognized his foolishness and erected a statue to Modesty in her honor. Her name is commonly explained "as a compound of *pênê* ('woof, thread') and *oloptô* ('to tear out') or *lepô* ('to strip off')'" (Kanavou 110); as such it reflects her role in the *Odyssey*, for the conjoining of weaving and tearing out are symbolic of "the trick played by Penelope on her suitors" (Kanavou 110). However, this is not the only possible origin. Another theory argues that her name comes from *penelops*, the word for "duck," a bird known for its monogamous habits; the duck is also the bird to which she owes her miraculous rescue in infancy in some versions of her story.

In the *Odyssey*, Penelope oversees Odysseus' estate and defends it against the voracious suitors. Though the story is centered on the hero's lengthy journey home after the Trojan War, scenes of life

at home on Ithaca reveal an intelligent woman simultaneously acting as the caring mother to a son, the object of unwanted attention from suitors, and the faithful wife of Odysseus.

As a woman beset by suitors, Penelope is described as a dangerous combination of beauty and cunning. She is described as “looking for all the world like Artemis or golden Aphrodite” (19.56-57; cf. 18.181-185, 18:235-242) with the focus placed heavily on her appearance when she is in the presence of the suitors. However, these visions of beauty are the means through which Penelope accomplishes her various goals. It is through her beauty that, near the end of the epic, she is able to “lur[e] gifts from her suitors..., / enchanting their hearts with suave seductive words / but all the while with something else in mind” (18.317-319). Most famously, she was able to stall her courtship by feigning to weave a burial shroud for Laertes.

Passage 1 on the handout, spoken by the suitor Antinous, reveals the nature of her relationship with the suitors: as the men continue to feast and lust after her, she is playing into their passions in order to further her own goals, revealing both her control and mental capabilities, qualities that make her an ideal partner to her husband. Indeed, Odysseus and Penelope are imaged as a perfect match. After Odysseus returns home in the guise of a beggar and makes a test of Penelope’s faithfulness (in Book 19), she, in turn, puts “her husband to the proof” (as Jack Winkler puts it). When Penelope requests that Eurycleia “move the study bed out of [the] bridal chamber” (in Book 23) Penelope feigns adultery to confirm the identity of Odysseus. The test of the bed thus proves her fidelity, as well as her wily and astute intellect (Winkler 1990, 157), and it also grants her a degree of control and agency (Winkler 1990, 133). Penelope and Odysseus, although acting in different gender spheres, are like-minded individuals who possess, and exert, their *metis* (cunning), in order to achieve their goals. To Homer, sameness of minds appears to be the mark of an ideal couple.

The love poet Ovid revisited the character of Penelope in his *Heroides*, or, *Heroines*, a collection of letters written from the perspectives of “women of the Heroic Age” (Hine 1991, ix).

One of the few women in these letters who receive a happy ending, Penelope writes to Ulysses (Odysseus) in hopes that he would soon return home.

Ovid draws strongly from the “Odyssean Penelope... [as] [a] paragon of wifely devotion and loyalty.” She waits for Ulysses, lamenting, “but you are not here, and I cannot guess the cause / of your protracted delay. In what part of the world / are you occupied, or taken captive, or hiding?” (lines 77-79) The weaving of the shroud is briefly alluded to (lines 14-17), and the letter focuses largely on the hero and his travels.

However, as Jill Connelly has persuasively argued, “in *Heroides* 1, Penelope no longer resembles the one-dimensional icon of fidelity and patience... but has become a more embittered queen who is growing less tolerant of her husband’s absence” (38). In the opening lines of the poem, Penelope’s tone and words reflect a wife impatient with her husband’s continued absence as she commands him, “never mind the favor of your reply; / but come yourself, at once” (lines 2-3). Aware that Troy has fallen and that Greek heroes have returned home, she has sent for news of Ulysses—in vain—and now muses [see passage 2 on the handout]: “Or are you a captive of love? / The hearts of men are fickle. Their eyes wander. / Do you sit with some femme fatale, joking about your / rustic / wife back home who is only good for weaving?” (lines 94-98) Here, Penelope is not simply concerned with Ulysses’ fidelity; instead, this depiction suggests “a hard-hearted man, who is not simply slow in returning, but actually hides from his family and his responsibilities at home” (Connelly 53). This strongly differentiates Ovid’s heroine from Homer’s; the latter would never have “cast Odysseus in an ill-light,” whereas the former allows her frustration at the asymmetry of their experiences to prevail (Jacobson 250).

Throughout the letter, Penelope wavers between depictions of her lonely and isolated existence and visions of the companionship, peace, and affection she longs for. Then, as her frustration with Ulysses’ absence and the weight of the pressure to remarry near the breaking point, she writes “for I

am only yours and will always be / Ulysses' wife" (lines 105-106). Albeit stated in language that is "rather stiff, formal, impassive, almost cold" (Jacobson 260), perhaps springing from a sense of duty, rather than from affection and love, Penelope's declaration enables her "to make a more concerted effort to achieve her husband's homecoming" (Connelly 57). An astute strategist, she focuses on "the neglect of [Ulysses'] familial responsibilities:" his estate on Ithaca is but "a powerless wife; Laertes, an old man; and your son, / Telemachus, who is still a stripling boy" (lines 123-124). They struggle against the weight of the suitors, whose actions towards her in particular are likened to a military assault, as the metaphor of war commonly conveys sexual aggression in Roman elegy; thus, she writes (passage 3 on the handout) "a wild and rowdy throng / ...assail me and beset my innocent life." (lines 109, 113). More importantly, however, by casting herself as the damsel in distress, Penelope "plays on Ulysses' heroic ethos and creates a setting that appeals to his zeal for battle and trickery" (Connelly 57). She adds [passage 4 on the handout] "Your son needs you now to teach him / how to be a man. Your father needs you also / and it is his prayer that you may return in time / to close his eyes on his last—and not so distant—day." (lines 138-141) These obligations are a source of guilt and shame for Ulysses, and by including them in the letter, without reference to herself, Penelope hopes that, even if he will not return for her sake, his concern for his father and son could entice him.

Ovid authored the *Heroides* during the reign of Augustus, whose "program of social and moral reform ... included new laws on marriage and adultery" (Joshel 2002, 165). This was a time of "imposed puritanism," and Howard Jacobson has argued that the *Heroides* offers a "deheroization of the mythic material and... [a] rejection of the male viewpoint, a denial of the Augustan...ideal" (Jacobson 7). While in his interpretation Penelope is "a dissatisfied, bitter woman, obsessed with sex, beset by self-pity, angry at her husband, and mourning for a lost life," thereby calling into question the very ideal of the *univira*, Penelope's reminding Ulysses of his obligation toward father

and son (that is, reminding him of the pietas he owes his familia), paradoxically subscribes to and upholds the Augustan program (Jacobson 274).

In sum, Ovid's vision of Penelope maintains the image of the loyal and patient wife while challenging the Odyssean exemplar: distraught with suitors, impatient with her husband, and more sensual than her epic counterpart (though perhaps not 'obsessed with sex,' as some have argued), she nonetheless remains worthy of admiration; Ovid reveals what he believes to be the real state of her psyche and restores a degree of humanity to the original flawless, loyal wife.^{1 2}

Born in Venice in 1364, Christine de Pizan moved to France at a young age. The first woman to earn her living exclusively through her writings, she worked in many literary genres, including poetry, biographies, and courtly manuals. In 1405 she authored *The Book of the City of Ladies* as a defense of women against the misogyny rampant in the writings of men. Christine set out to disprove many of the negative stereotypes about women by providing examples of intelligent, capable, and virtuous women, such as Sappho, the Amazons, and Queen Fredegunde of France. In one section, where she explored the claim that "chastity is the supreme virtue in a woman," Christine sought to prove that, despite what men say, women are capable of chastity (Pizan 1999, 141). Penelope is offered as an example of a righteous and honorable pagan woman.

In her representation of Penelope, Christine emphasizes her virtuous chastity to the exclusion of her appearance and intellect. She writes that, "despite the fact that she was courted by various kings and princes for her great beauty, she refused to listen to a single word they said" (Pizan 1999, 144) and when Odysseus returns home, he "found her assailed by a king who was attracted by her extraordinary virtue and purity" (Pizan 1999, 144).

¹ Ovid's image of Penelope is one that will be used by later authors, including Shakespeare in *Coriolanus*, when the character Valeria reprimands Virgilia: "You would be another Penelope: yet, they say, all the yarn she spun in Ulysses' absence did but fill Ithaca full of moths" (*Coriolanus*, Act I, scene III).

² Ovid mentioned Penelope in his other works as well; in the *Ars Amatoria*, Ovid advises, "Once steadfast you'll conquer Penelope herself in time," and in the *Amores*, he simply states that, despite a lack of supervision, she remained faithful.

Christine's depiction of Penelope is extremely selective: there is no account of the trick of the shroud, the challenge of the bow, or her test of Odysseus's identity. Even though Christine mentions that Penelope possesses "other qualities," and was "wise and prudent," she pays these no mind and instead continuously emphasizes that she was "particularly prized for her chastity" (Pizan 1999, 144). This one-dimensional presentation of Penelope, which extends to many other women in her book, has been tailored for Christine's purpose and audience, and the Homeric example is discussed only in light of how the author wishes her to be known.

Although from a modern perspective this narrow vision of Penelope would hardly be considered feminist, "Christine's voice in defence of women ... was in its time a dissenting voice" (xxiv). She compiled this piece during a period rife with misogyny (xvii), when literature itself was considered the preserve of men. The male authors who were her contemporaries relied heavily on previous sources, quoting them selectively, "citing the bad things that their favourite authorities said about women and leaving out the good" (xxiii-xxiv). Christine cleverly utilized the same "method of selective quotation against them," and by "deriv[ing] the bulk of her pro-woman material from well-known and authoritative sources," she "could therefore cite exactly the same authorities as they did whilst taking the good said (sic) of women and leaving out the bad." (xxiv, xxx)

Since Christine was rebuking both contemporary and ancient authors,³ many of whom pointed out the dearth of women such as Penelope and Lucretia signaled the end of virtuous women, and stressed the dangers of deceitful women, she had to strip Penelope of her wiles in order to preserve her as the archetypal faithful wife. Her reductive vision of Penelope as the patriarchal ideal, then, is

³ It is difficult to know exactly which contemporary and classical texts Christine has access to, as well as how these texts influenced her work. The few texts that can be known with absolute certainty are those she explicitly cites, such as Giovanni Boccaccio's *De Claris Mulieribus*, or, *Concerning Famous Women* (1374). In terms of Latin texts, she strongly rebukes Ovid and his *Amores* and *The Art of Love*; however, she draws from his *Metamorphosis* on a few occasions. Ultimately, however, it is relatively irrelevant how previous authors envisioned Penelope; whether she was wily or faithful, Christine's agenda, and selective quoting, were focused on refuting the negative claims against women.

a sacrifice for a nobler cause, that of showing that faithful and chaste women have always existed, be they pagan or Christian.

The rise of Feminism and the explosion of feminist scholarship in the 20th century have prompted an earnest reevaluation of Penelope, as in Margaret Atwood's *The Penelopiad*. Employing sources such as the *Odyssey* and Graves' *Greek Myths*, Atwood weaves a rich narrative spoken by the deceased Penelope now in Hades, tracing her life from childhood through Odysseus' homecoming and providing a "radical re-gendering" of the myth (191).

The facts of Atwood's novella align with what can be gathered from the *Odyssey*: Odysseus serves in the Trojan War, leaving Penelope to raise Telemachus, wait, weep, and weave; Odysseus returns home and slaughters the suitors, servants, and maids. Not surprisingly, Atwood's Penelope retains attributes of the epic model—her fidelity, her weeping, and her weaving, minus her physical beauty—but Atwood's attempt to piece together a life story from Penelope's point of view complicates the traditional elements. In the novella, Penelope describes how "tediously" faithful she'd been while waiting for Odysseus, displaying the self-awareness of a character who looks at herself as a literary persona (this is passage 5 on the handout): "Hadn't I been faithful? Hadn't I waited, and waited, and waited, despite the temptation—almost the compulsion—to do otherwise? And what did I amount to, once the official version gained ground? An edifying legend. A stick used to beat other women with" (Atwood 2005, 2). In *The Penelopiad*, Penelope's weeping for the return of her husband is, wittily, attributed to her ancestry: "excessive weeping... is a handicap of Naiad-born" (Atwood 2005, 10). And, finally, her cunning intelligence is not a trait to be teased out by a clever reader: Penelope self-consciously boasts of the deliberate part she had in the denouement of the *Odyssey* (passage 6 on the handout):

The songs claim that the arrival of Odysseus and my decision to set the test of the bow and axes coincided by accident... [But] I knew that only Odysseus would be able to perform this archery trick. I knew that the beggar was Odysseus. There was no coincidence. I set the whole thing up on purpose. (Atwood 2005, 139)

Atwood's Penelope is a multifaceted character whose complexity is unpacked by Penelope herself. The novella introduces new elements, including Penelope's particularly close association with water. The speech her mother (a water nymph) delivers at Penelope's wedding reveals Atwood's view of Penelope [handout passage 7]: "Water does not resist. Water flows... Water is patient. Dripping water wears away a stone... Remember you are half water. If you can't go through an obstacle, go around it. Water does" (Atwood 2005, 43). Women in antiquity were considered wet (Carson 1990, 137), but whereas wetness was usually associated with the instability of emotion, Penelope's own watery nature is at the core of her resilience and strength. Weeping is but the outward sign of her nature, while at her inner core lie determined patience and resourcefulness, as also evidenced in the weaving and unraveling of the shroud, for thread is shape shifting as well.

There is also the connection between Penelope and her maids. As Thomas Jenkins has recently argued in his *Antiquity Now*, "Penelope creates in effect a surrogate, substitute family of women: from the mother-substitute of Eurycleia to the daughter-substitutes of the handmaidens" (197). In Atwood's narrative, the maids "were [Penelope's] sources of information" about the suitors, her "eyes and ears in the palace, and it was they who helped [her] pick away [her] weaving" (Atwood 2005, 30, 114). Throughout the novella, the maids act as a Greek Chorus, offering haunting songs and poems. In the section titled "An Anthropology Lecture," the twelve maids assume the persona of the "companions of Artemis, virginal but deadly goddess of the moon," with Penelope serving as "the High Priestess, the incarnation of Artemis herself" (Atwood 2005, 164-5).

In Atwood's retelling, we can recognize how truly limited our perceptions of Penelope had been, for in the previously described visions of her, we see her as only half to a whole: in *The Odyssey*, Penelope serves primarily as the property of Odysseus, and in other depictions, she is only the faithful wife waiting for her husband, even if exhausted and impatient in Ovid. In *The*

Penelopiad however, Atwood allows the reader to witness characteristics found in *The Odyssey* on a more intimate level.

Odysseus' story, though indispensable to Penelope's, is deemphasized and Penelope emerges as defined by relationships and attachments that transcend those she traditionally nourishes exclusively towards Odysseus and his oikos. Restored to the company of women, Penelope emerges as more elemental, rebellious, lucid, and cynical. This vision of Penelope is one in which detailed accounts are provided on how she managed and grew her husband's estate and renown. We are exposed to the Penelope who, instead of performing the anaklypteria out of modesty, draws her veil to hide her laughter as her father chases after the marriage chariot, for "there was something humorous about a father who'd once tossed his own child into the sea capering down the road after that very child." (49) In her relationship with Helen, the depth of Penelope's fears of her husband's infidelity and her physical insecurities emerge; she ponders why "[Odysseus] was still—and possible always—thinking about Helen," as she repeatedly emphasizes a dichotomy between Helen and herself, beauty and intelligence (64). Penelope's cynical remarks throughout the novella reveal an astute mind and awareness of both social and personal situations. Before her wedding, she likens herself to "a sort of gilded blood pudding," for the suitors were not interested in "Penelope the Duck. It's only what comes with me—the royal connection, the pile of glittering junk" (39, 29). Moreover, she comments on Odysseus' reputation as a master of wiles when she writes that his epic "was a likely story. But then, all of his stories were likely" (174). These insights into Penelope's character reveal nothing that is not already found in the *Odyssey*; instead, Atwood encourages the reader to fully comprehend otherwise stifled attributes as we engage with Penelope's mind as opposed to Homer's.

The character of Penelope has undergone numerous transitions over the course of her literary existence with baser elements from *The Odyssey*, such as her fidelity and weaving, remaining.

Christine de Pizan's vision of Penelope remains truest to the original, with a narrow focus placed heavily on her chastity in her husband's absence. This selective interpretation of Penelope's character, for potentially feminist reasons, ultimately accomplishes little. Ovid and Atwood, however, allow Penelope more freedom. In Ovid's reimagining of her, Penelope's character becomes more vocal about concerns of her husband's whereabouts and frustration at his extended absence. This version both questions contemporary Roman mores while paradoxically subscribing to Augustan principles as Ovid reexamines Penelope's psychological state and infuses her character with realistic standards. Atwood, too, envisions a more intricate Penelope, yet approaches the matter differently. Instead of a Penelope who is only waiting for her husband, this character is more active and more intricate. She has a deeper backstory, with complex emotions, as she is seen running the operations of her husband's estate and leading a fuller life. These various attempts to examine life through Penelope's eyes have created a character transcendent of the original mythology as she remains a relevant presence in the theatre of feminist research.

Through Penelope's Eyes: from Atwood to Homer
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1. Homer, *Odyssey*, 2. 94-122.

It's not the suitors here who deserve the blame,
it's... the matchless queen of cunning.
Look here. For three years now, getting on to four,
she's played it fast and loose with all our hearts,
building each man's hopes—
dangling promises, dropping hints to each—
but all the while with something else in mind.
This was her latest masterpiece of guile:
she set up a great loom in the royal halls
and she began to weave, and the weaving finespun,
the yarns endless, and she would lead us on: 'Young men,
my suitors, now that King Odysseus is no more,
go slowly, keen as you are to marry me, until
I can finish off this web...
so my weaving won't all fray and come to nothing.
This is a shroud for old lord Laertes, for that day
when the deadly fate that lays us out at last will take him down.
I dread the shame my countrywomen would heap upon me,
yes, if a man of such wealth should lie in state
without a shroud for cover.'

Her very words,
and despite our pride and passion we believed her.
So by day she'd weave at her great and growing web—
by night, by the light of torches set beside her,
she would unravel all she'd done. Three whole years
she deceived us blind, seduced us with this scheme...
Then, when the wheeling seasons brought the fourth year on,
one of her women, in on the queen's secret, told the truth
and we caught her in the act—unweaving her gorgeous web.
So she finished it off. Against her will. We forced her."

Trans. Robert Fagles

2. Ovid, *Heroides*, 1. 94-98

"Or are you a captive of love?
The hearts of men are fickle. Their eyes wander.
Do you sit with some femme fatale, joking about your
rustic
wife back home who is only good for weaving?"

Trans. David R. Slavitt

3. Ovid, *Heroides*, 1. 109, 113.

“a wild and rowdy throng
 ...assail me and beset my innocent life.”
 Turba ruunt in me luxuriosa proci

Trans. David R. Slavitt

4. Ovid, *Heroides*, 1. 138-141

“Your son needs you now to teach him
 how to be a man. Your father needs you also
 and it is his prayer that you may return in time
 to close his eyes on his last—and not so distant—day.”

Trans. David R. Slavitt

5. Atwood, *The Penelopiad*, p. 2

“Hadn’t I been faithful? Hadn’t I waited, and waited, and waited, despite the temptation—almost the compulsion—to do otherwise? And what did I amount to, once the official version gained ground? An edifying legend. A stick used to beat other women with.”

6. Atwood, *The Penelopiad*, p. 139

“The songs claim that the arrival of Odysseus and my decision to set the test of the bow and axes coincided by accident... [But] I knew that only Odysseus would be able to perform this archery trick. I knew that the beggar was Odysseus. There was no coincidence. I set the whole thing up on purpose.”

7. Atwood, *The Penelopiad*, p. 43

“Water does not resist. Water flows... Water is patient. Dripping water wears away a stone... Remember you are half water. If you can’t go through an obstacle, go around it. Water does.”

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